

When Severe Hypothyroidism Mimics Neuromuscular Diseases: A Case Supporting Outpatient Management in Modern Endocrinology

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Abstract

Background: Severe hypothyroidism may present with symptoms similar to those of primary neuromuscular or acute neurological disorders, resulting in diagnostic delays and potentially unnecessary hospitalizations.

Case presentation: A 40-year-old man arrived at the emergency department (ED) because of postural instability, diplopia, myalgia, and elevated creatine kinase (CK), suggestive of a neuromuscular disorder. Labs revealed thyrotropin (TSH) levels over 170 $\mu\text{U}/\text{mL}$ and suppressed free thyroxine (fT₄). Despite severe biochemical parameters, clinical stability allowed for outpatient management with levothyroxine administration and endocrinological follow-up.

Discussion: The case mimicked inflammatory myopathy or brainstem stroke, but the absence of 'red flags' allowed for safe outpatient treatment. Literature confirms that hypothyroidism can present with neurologic signs and that structured outpatient pathways are effective.

Conclusion: This case highlights the importance of recognizing endocrine causes in neuromuscular presentations and supports outpatient management models for stable hypothyroid patients.

Keywords: hypothyroidism; myopathy; neuromuscular disorders; subacute neurological disorders; outpatient management; sustainability of healthcare system.

Introduction

The increasing demand for hospital resources compels healthcare systems, such as Italy's National Healthcare System (NHS), to reevaluate the need of hospital admissions, particularly for subacute and chronic conditions. Within this context, endocrinology emerges as a discipline well-suited to outpatient care models. Although traditional management of severe hypothyroidism favors inpatient admission due to risks such as myxedema coma, there is growing evidence that many cases, despite pronounced biochemical abnormalities, do not present with clinical instability and can be safely managed in outpatient settings, avoiding an economic burden on the healthcare system. [1][2]

Case presentation

A 40-year-old man presented to the emergency department (ED) with a subacute onset of postural instability, diplopia, fatigue, and diffuse myalgia. He appeared weak and slow in both movement and speech. Physical examination revealed periocular edema, a heart rate of 60 bpm, and arterial blood pressure of 110/70 mmHg. There was no hepatosplenomegaly and no focal limb weakness. Neurological examination was otherwise unremarkable.

Laboratory results showed a markedly elevated thyrotropin (TSH) level of 172 μ U/mL (ULN < 4.2), suppressed free thyroxine (fT4: 0.04 ng/dL, LLN > 0.90), and elevated levels of creatin-kinase (CK: 4588 U/L, ULN < 200) and creatinine (1.48 mg/dL, ULN < 1.2), with an estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR, using CKD-EPI equation) of 59.2 mL/min/1.73m². Despite these concerning biochemical markers, the patient was alert, hemodynamically stable, and showed no signs of respiratory or cardiac compromise. Nevertheless, admission to the internal medicine department was requested by the ED staff.

After consultation with the endocrinology service, a diagnosis of severe primary hypothyroidism was established, oral levothyroxine was initiated at a dose of 50 μ g/day, and the patient was discharged home with careful follow-up in the endocrinology outpatient clinic.

On day four, TSH remained elevated while fT4 showed slight improvement (0.15 ng/dL). The dose of levothyroxine was increased to 75 μ g/day. By day nine, further biochemical and clinical improvement was noted. On day twenty, with a serum TSH concentration of 64 μ U/mL (fT4 0.73 ng/dL), marked symptomatic relief and the absence of palpitations were noted, and the dose was titrated to 100 μ g/day. Anti-thyroid peroxidase antibodies were elevated, supporting a diagnosis of chronic autoimmune thyroiditis. Thyroid ultrasound showed a small, hypoechoic gland. A neurological assessment excluded central nervous system involvement.

Discussion

This case highlights the variety of presentations of hypothyroidism and its ability to mimic both neuromuscular disorders and acute neurological syndromes. The constellation of symptoms — diplopia, gait imbalance, elevated CK— initially suggested differential diagnoses including inflammatory myopathies or even brainstem ischemia [3][4]. The diagnostic complexity is further compounded by non-specific findings such as fatigue and mental slowing, often attributed to psychiatric or systemic illnesses. Hypothyroidism can present with polyneuropathy, entrapment syndromes, and even cerebellar dysfunction, all of which contribute to diagnostic delay [5-8]. Nevertheless, the absence of clinical red flags enabled a management strategy focused on outpatient care.

The final diagnosis was chronic autoimmune (Hashimoto's) thyroiditis with severe hypothyroidism, myocytolysis, and initial acute renal failure. Although the clinical problem was severe, the patient was correctly treated as an outpatient in the endocrinology medical office.

Clinical stability, specialist access, and timely follow-up proved decisive in avoiding hospitalization, resulting in a better use of public healthcare system resources.

Conclusion

Severe hypothyroidism, when presenting with neuromuscular symptoms, can closely resemble primary neurological or muscular pathologies. The present case illustrates how endocrine disorders may deceptively manifest as neurological emergencies. Yet, it also reinforces that biochemical severity alone should not impose hospitalization in the absence of hemodynamic or neurocognitive instability [1] [2].

The successful outpatient management of this case demonstrates the potential of integrated care pathways that combine emergency medicine with endocrinology. Such approaches can enhance diagnostic accuracy, promote resource stewardship, and improve patient outcomes. By rethinking rigid hospitalization paradigms, healthcare systems can embrace models that are both clinically sound and economically sustainable [1][2].

Figure 1. Framework for integrating outpatient management and hospitalization.

Legend.

PATIENT SELECTION Identify criteria for admitting only those who require inpatient care	<i>Patient selection.</i> Establish clear clinical criteria to identify patients who truly require hospitalization, avoiding unnecessary admissions and promoting safe outpatient management.
CARE COORDINATION Implement seamless communication between inpatient and outpatient settings	<i>Care coordination.</i> Encourage seamless and ongoing communication between healthcare professionals across hospital and outpatient settings to ensure a unified view of the patient's journey.
TRANSITIONAL CARE Develop robust protocols for discharges, follow-ups, and home visits	<i>Transitional care.</i> Develop structured protocols for discharge, post-hospital follow-ups, and home visits to reduce the risk of readmission and improve continuity of care.
RESOURCE UTILIZATION Optimize the use of hospital facilities and outpatient services	<i>Resource utilization.</i> Strategically use hospital infrastructure and outpatient services to maximize efficiency, lower costs, and maintain high-quality care.

Statements

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Data availability

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Author contributions

BP and MA conceived and wrote the manuscript. MA made the figure. All authors reviewed the manuscript and its final version, approving its contents.

Conflict of interest

All authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Ethical approval

This article is based on previously published data and does not involve any new studies on human participants or animals.

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